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who consulted pediatricians showed less hesitancy than parents who called general practitioners. Raising public confidence and understanding about vaccinations has been shown to be an effective way to improve knowledge and build public trust. This is especially true when focusing on low- and middle-income areas and directly addressing the information gap that prevents some people from getting vaccinated.

Aim. To study the attitude of parents to immunization and to determine its effect on immunization.

Materials and methods: *Survey.* To learn more about parents' thoughts on children's vaccinations, a survey was given to parents. *Data analysis.* Case-control. Extensive indicators and their errors were computed in order to analyze the data that was obtained. The rates in the case and control groups were compared using the odds ratio. Student's test was used to evaluate the difference between the indicators ($p < 0.05$). Also, the correlation between the indicators was ascertained. The analysis of statistical data was carried out in the Origin.lab 10.0 application software package.

Results. Mothers participated in our survey. Because mothers tend to children the majority of the time in our nation. Because they are better informed about their children's health, mothers visit polyclinics to get immunizations and medical exams.

Mothers in the main survey group were $29.3 \pm 0.3\%$ of the average age, while mothers in the control group were $26.2 \pm 0.5\%$ of the average age. The gender distribution of vaccinated and unvaccinated children revealed that $43.4 \pm 4.3\%$ of vaccinated children were girls and $56.6 \pm 4.8\%$ of boys. The corresponding ratios for individuals who did not receive the vaccine were $41.7 \pm 4.9\%$ and $58.3 \pm 5.4\%$. Based on this, we can infer that boys were more likely than girls to have received vaccinations ($p < 0.05$). A child's history of chronic illness is mentioned as one of the reasons vaccinations are not recommended in a number of studies. It was also verified in our questionnaire that children with chronic illnesses have an impact on the immunization procedure. Out of them, $3.9 \pm 1.7\%$ of children who received vaccinations had chronic diseases, while $96.1 \pm 2.1\%$ did not. In children who were not vaccinated, this indicator was $70.9 \pm 4.2\%$ and $29.1 \pm 5.1\%$, respectively. This indicates that a reduction in the coverage of immunization protocols occurs when children have chronic conditions ($p < 0.001$). "Which educational institution does the child go to?" We examined the responses to the query. Students at State Pre-School Education Institutions made up the largest percentage (63.8 ± 4.9) of the youngsters who received the immunization. The largest proportion of children who were cared for at home by their parents or nannies among those who did not receive vaccines was $86.6 \pm 4.1\%$.

Conclusion. Compared to children who attend public preschool, children in the care of parents or nannies have lower vaccination coverage rates. At-home parents are overly cautious about their kids because they think that vaccinations won't have any impact on their health.

HUMAN PAPILLOMAVIRUS VACCINATION IN LOW-RESOURCE SETTINGS – OVERCOMING BARRIERS TO IMPLEMENTATION

Virmani S., Sattarova K. A.

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Introduction: Human Papillomavirus (HPV) vaccination is a proven strategy for preventing cervical cancer and other HPV-related malignancies. Despite its efficacy, vaccine uptake remains low in low- and middle-income countries due to financial, cultural, and infrastructural barriers. High-income nations have achieved high coverage through national immunization programs, but many resource-limited settings still struggle. This study examines the key obstacles to HPV vaccination in six low-resource countries while exploring successful strategies to improve implementation.

Aim: This study aims to identify barriers to HPV vaccination in resource-limited settings and propose evidence-based strategies to increase coverage. By analyzing vaccination trends across different economic settings, this research highlights interventions that can enhance HPV immunization programs.

Materials and Methods: This study analyzed HPV vaccination data and policies (2000–2024) across six countries, with a case study from Uzbekistan's School No. 38 highlighting implementation success. Ethical approval was obtained for a local survey.

Results: Cost remains a significant barrier, with HPV vaccines priced at \$75 per dose in India and Pakistan, rendering them inaccessible for many. In contrast, high-income countries like Australia and the UK offer free vaccinations, achieving coverage rates exceeding 70%. Vaccine hesitancy further restricts uptake, particularly in Russia, where anti-vaccine sentiment prevails, and Pakistan, where cultural and religious beliefs influence decision-making. Disparities in healthcare infrastructure also impact vaccine accessibility; Ukraine's political instability disrupts immunization efforts, while Sri Lanka and Uzbekistan continue expanding programs despite logistical challenges. A school-based vaccination program at "OROM" General Secondary School No. 38 in Uzbekistan serves as an effective model. Among 18 girls aged 9 to 10 years, 17 received the first dose in March 2024, and 15 completed the second dose at school, while two received it at a local healthcare centre. One student remained unvaccinated due to illness. The government-funded program reported no adverse effects, demonstrating that school-based immunization campaigns can enhance HPV vaccination rates in resource-limited settings.

Low-income countries like Rwanda and Bhutan have achieved coverage rates exceeding 90% through government funding and international partnerships. Upper-middle-income nations such as Brazil and South Africa show

moderate progress but face challenges with rural access. Clinical studies confirm that HPV vaccination reduces cervical cancer incidence by more than 50% and significantly lowers rates of genital warts and other HPV-related malignancies. The vaccine provides cross-protective immunity, safeguarding against multiple HPV strains. Double-blind randomized trials confirm long-term efficacy, with no serious adverse effects reported.

Conclusions: HPV vaccination is a highly effective and cost-efficient strategy for reducing cervical cancer and HPV-related diseases, yet financial, cultural, and healthcare infrastructure challenges continue to hinder its widespread adoption. School-based programs, government subsidies, and public awareness initiatives have proven successful in improving vaccination rates. Countries must adopt evidence-based strategies, leverage international funding, and strengthen healthcare systems to achieve the World Health Organization's goal of 90% HPV vaccination coverage by 2030.

PHARMACOECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF DRUGS USED IN THE TREATMENT OF MULTIPLE MYELOMA AND HYGIENIC JUSTIFICATION OF NUTRITIONAL RATION

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Abstract. Multiple myeloma (MM) is a hematological malignancy that requires complex pharmacotherapy, often involving VCD (Bortezomib, Cyclophosphamide, and Dexamethasone), VRD (Bortezomib, Lenalidomide, and Dexamethasone), and VMP (Bortezomib, Melphalan, and Prednisolone) regimens. However, gastrointestinal (GI) adverse effects are prevalent among patients undergoing these treatments, which significantly impact their quality of life. Given the high cost of VRD and Dara-VRD regimens in Uzbekistan, the VCD regimen is commonly used, necessitating strategies to mitigate its GI-related adverse effects.

This study aims to analyze the pharmacoeconomic aspects of MM treatment in Uzbekistan while developing optimized nutritional strategies to minimize GI toxicity.

Methods. The study consists of three phases:

Microbiological Analysis: Evaluation of gut microbiota alterations due to MM therapy through stool sample analysis.

Probiotic Intervention: Administration of probiotics to counteract dysbiosis and improve GI health.

Optimized Nutrition Strategy: Implementation of a diet tailored to reduce inflammation and enhance nutrient absorption, focusing on locally available, cost-effective food options.

Results and Discussion. Preliminary findings suggest that VCD therapy leads to notable GI side effects, including diarrhea, mucositis, and dysbiosis. Probiotic supplementation demonstrated a positive impact on gut microbiota composition, potentially reducing GI complications. Furthermore, the introduction of a structured dietary regimen improved nutritional status and overall well-being of patients.

Conclusion. Addressing GI adverse effects in MM therapy through a pharmacoeconomic and nutritional approach is crucial. The proposed strategy of microbiome modulation and dietary optimization could enhance treatment adherence, reduce healthcare costs, and improve patient outcomes. Further large-scale studies are required to validate these findings and integrate them into clinical practice.

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